

6 5 4 3 2 1

D

C

4x M3.5 HOLES

B

Hole Placements as per TO-3 Layout

A

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION	
TITLE: CCR HOUSING			
DWG NO. 1-2			A4
SCALE:1:2			SHEET 1 OF 1